

SUPPLEMENTAL FIGURE 1

Supplemental Figure 1. Pharmacokinetic predictions for PAH using its clinically observed plasma intravenous clearance value. To test the accuracy of the drug-dependent input parameters toward further building a MechKiM-PBPK model for OAT1, the first simulation used the clinically-observed plasma clearance of PAH following a $10 \text{ mg} \cdot \text{kg}^{-1}$ intravenous dose ($CL_{i.v.}$), which is reported as $40.6 \text{ L} \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$ (Prescott et al., 1993). The observed plasma concentration-time profiles for PAH are from Hirata-Dulas et al. 1994 and Prescott et al. 1993. Both studies administered a 10 mg/kg intravenous dose of PAH to healthy volunteers. The ‘drug-dependent’ parameters used for PAH were as follows. The molecular weight, LogP and pK_a were $194.2 \text{ g} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$, -2.2 and 3.83 (Smith et al., 1945), respectively. We used the ‘default’ blood-to-plasma partition ratio (B/P) of one, and the measured fraction unbound in plasma (f_{up}) of 0.83 (Smith et al., 1945). Using the Full PBPK model, Method 2 (Rodgers and Rowland, 2007), and a K_p scalar of one, the predicted steady-state volume of distribution (V_{ss}) was $0.29 \text{ L} \cdot \text{kg}^{-1}$, which approximates the observed V_{ss} of $0.23 \text{ L} \cdot \text{kg}^{-1}$ (Prescott et al., 1993). When using the initial drug-dependent parameters and the observed plasma $CL_{i.v.}$, the simulated and observed plasma concentration-time profiles were in good agreement with each other indicating that the drug-dependent input parameters were appropriate for further model development using MechKiM.